

Synthesis, crystal structure and thermal studies of catena-(L-glutamato)-aqua copper(II) monohydrate

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The synthesis, crystal structure and thermal study of the blue catena-(L-glutamato)-aqua copper(II) monohydrate have been reported. The compound crystallizes in $P2_12_12_1$ space group and consists of a polymeric three-dimensional network of copper(II) which is coordinated with the amino nitrogen and the carboxylate oxygen of L-glutamato, the side chain carboxylate oxygen of a neighbouring L-glutamato and the oxygen of a water molecule in the equatorial position. Weak coordination of two additional glutamate oxygen atoms to both the axial positions completes a distorted octahedron. The crystal structure shows that the lattice water is stabilized by the formation of strong H-bonding network with the coordinated water molecule. Removal and reabsorption of the water molecule have been studied by thermal analysis.

The design and synthesis of microporous inorganic materials mimicking zeolite are of current interest for their widespread application in heterogeneous catalysis, adsorption, selective binding of the guest molecules etc.¹. Self-assembly is the most efficient approach towards the construction of such types of molecular systems. The H-bonding plays a very important role for the generation of such molecules and also for the host-guest relationship. Crystal structure of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-glu}(\text{H}_2\text{O}))\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (glu = glutamate) revealed that it is a self-assembled, three-dimensional coordination polymer². However, the structure was determined by the Weissenberg photographic method² and the H-bonding network which is very important for the properties of such compounds, was not analyzed. We have therefore reexamined the structure with greater precision, shown the H-bonding network and studied the host-guest relationship by thermogravimetry.

Results and discussion

Description of the structure of the title complex (1) :

The structure consists of a polymeric three-dimensional network in which each copper atom is coordinated in a distorted octahedral geometry (Fig. 1) by three glutamate ions and one water molecule which is linked to another non-coordinated water molecule by H-bonding network. The four donor atoms which form the equatorial plane are the water O(100) at a 1.987(5) Å and γ -carboxylate O(11) at 1.973(5) Å of a L-glutamato, the α -carboxylate O(O2_4) at 1.968(5) Å and the amino N(N5_4) at 2.001(5) Å of a second L-glutamato ion which acts as bidentate ligand, forming a five

membered glycine like chelate ring (Fig. 1). The bond distances agree well with those reported for the Cu^{II} complexes with amino acids³. The coordination of the axial po-

Fig. 1. Ortep-3 view of the title complex with the atom labeling scheme. Thermal ellipsoids are shown at 50% probability.

sitions are completed by a α -carboxylate O(O1_2) at 2.288(5) Å of a third ligand and a very weakly coordinated γ -carboxylate O(10) at 2.587(6) Å of the first ligand. Thus, each L-glutamato ligand bridges three Cu^{II} centres via che-

lating γ -carboxylate to one Cu^{II} , chelating amine N and one of α -carboxylate to another Cu^{II} and a monodentate α -carboxylate O to a third Cu^{II} .

The relevant crystal data are summarized in Table 1. Selected bond lengths and angles are listed in Table 2. Fractional Coordinates and Equivalent Isotropic Thermal Parameters of the non-hydrogen atoms of the complex are given in Table 3.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement details of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-glu})(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Formula	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{CuNO}_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
<i>M</i>	244.70
Crystal system	Orthorhombic
Space group	$P2_12_12_1$
<i>a</i> /Å	7.232(11)
<i>b</i> /Å	10.311(14)
<i>c</i> /Å	11.058(14)
<i>V</i> /Å ³	825(2)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>D_c</i> /g cm ⁻³	1.970
<i>F</i> ₀₀₀	500
μ/mm^{-1} [Mo-K α]	2.647
No. of unique data	1472
No. of data with $I > 2\sigma(I)$	1409
<i>R₁</i> , <i>wR₂</i>	0.0453, 0.1149

Table 2. Bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of the title complex with e.s.d.'s in parentheses

Cu1-O10	2.587(6)
Cu1-O11	1.973(5)
Cu1-O1_2	2.288(5)
Cu1-O2_4	1.968(5)
Cu1-N5_4	2.001(5)
Cu1-O100	1.987(5)
O10-Cu1-O11	56.05(13)
O11-Cu1-O1_2	93.85(13)
O1_2-Cu1-O2_4	100.89(13)
O2_4-Cu1-N5_4	83.31(16)
N5_4-Cu1-O100	92.67(18)
O100-Cu1-O10	80.84(17)
O10-Cu1-O1_2	147.79(12)
O10-Cu1-O2_4	92.33(16)
O10-Cu1-N5_4	117.16(14)
O11-Cu1-O2_4	92.32(14)
O11-Cu1-N5_4	171.92(16)
O11-Cu1-O100	90.47(16)
O1_2-Cu1-N5_4	93.64(15)
O1_2-Cu1-O100	89.02(15)
O2_4-Cu1-O100	169.49(17)

(_2) designates the symmetry related atom at $1-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$.

(_4) designates the symmetry related atom at $1/2-x, 1-y, 1/2+z$.

Table 3. Fractional coordinates and equivalent isotropic thermal parameters of the non-hydrogen atoms of the title complex

Atom	<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>U</i> (eq)[Å ²]
Cu1	0.60031(7)	0.43316(5)	0.47087(5)	0.0188(2)
O1	0.1255(5)	0.8790(3)	0.1191(3)	0.0270(11)
O2	0.0184(5)	0.7381(4)	-0.0169(3)	0.0259(11)
O10	0.2852(6)	0.5506(5)	0.4539(3)	0.0344(13)
O11	0.4759(5)	0.4715(3)	0.3162(3)	0.0255(11)
O100	0.6874(6)	0.6155(4)	0.4819(4)	0.0327(11)
N5	-0.1907(6)	0.6092(4)	0.1373(3)	0.0217(11)
C3	0.0296(6)	0.7850(5)	0.0884(4)	0.0197(12)
C4	-0.0805(6)	0.7157(4)	0.1901(4)	0.0180(12)
C6	0.0506(7)	0.6682(5)	0.2887(4)	0.0227(14)
C7	0.2076(6)	0.5820(5)	0.2430(4)	0.0250(14)
C8	0.3275(7)	0.5320(4)	0.3451(4)	0.0210(12)
O200	0.5160(5)	0.8456(4)	0.4055(3)	0.0280(11)

U(eq) = 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalized *U* tensor.

The two H-atoms of the uncoordinated water molecules are strongly H-bonded with the γ -carboxylate O(11) and O(10) and its oxygen atom O(200) is acceptor of two H-bonds formed by the two symmetry related coordinated water molecules (Table 4, Fig. 2). Thus the lattice water forms an extensive H-bonding network.

Table 4. Hydrogen bonding distances (Å) and angles (°) of the title complex

D-H...A	D-H	D...A	H...A	\angle D-H...A
N5-H5A...O2 ^k	0.90	2.946(7)	2.23	136
O100-H101...O200	0.89	2.807(7)	1.94	168
O100-H102...O200 ^e	0.86	2.713(7)	1.95	147
O200-H201...O10 ^f	0.90	2.712(7)	1.82	171
O200-H202...O11 ⁱ	0.89	2.775(6)	1.90	171

Symmetry equivalent :

k) $-1/2+x, 3/2-y, -z$

e) $1/2+x, 3/2-y, 1-z$

i) $-x, y+1/2, -z+1/2$

Fig. 2. An illustration of the hydrogen bonding interactions in the complex in the solid state.

Thermal analysis :

The TG-DTA analysis of the title compound (Fig. 3) shows that it starts losing water molecules at $\sim 90^\circ$ and become anhydrous in a single step at 140° . The observed mass loss corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water (obs. 14.2%; calcd. 14.7%). Although there are two types of

Fig. 3. The simultaneous TG and DTA curves for compound **1** (—) and **1a** (---) (sample mass 10.64 and 10.59 mg for compound **1** and **1a** respectively).

water molecules in the compound, one is coordinated and the other is in the lattice, no break in the TG/DTG curve was observed corroborating the X-ray result that the water molecules are strongly linked to each other by H-bond. The dehydrated species on keeping in open atmosphere (relative humidity 60–80%) for several hours, reabsorb only one molecule of water and transforms into **1a** as is evident from thermal analysis (Fig. 3; obs. 6.9%; calcd. 7.3%). The second molecule of water has not been reabsorbed even on keeping it in the open atmosphere for a month. It is very difficult to conclude whether the water molecule in the monohydrated species (**1a**) is coordinated or is in the lattice. However, as it is found in the crystal structure of **1**, the lattice water is stabilized by formation of the strong H-bonding network with the coordinated water i.e. it should exist only in the presence of the later. Therefore, the water molecule in the monohydrated compound is most likely coordinated to the Cu^{II} . The same starting temperature for dehydration of both the monohydrated (**1a**) and dihydrated (**1**) species indicates that the dehydration is probably initiated by the loss of coordinated water, as it is present in both of them.

It is to be noted that if the dehydrated species is kept in suspension in water or in rectified spirit for *ca.* one hour it reabsorbs two molecules of water to revert into the title complex.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the title compound show a broad band at

3221 cm^{-1} due to the stretching vibrations of the NH_2 group of the tridentate ligand, L-glutamic acid. Another band which appears at 3318 cm^{-1} can be attributed to ν_{as} (O–H) of the water molecule. The lowering of the ν_{as} (O–H) frequency of water molecule is due to its involvement in strong hydrogen bonding. The ν_{as} (O–H) of water molecule in **1a** appears at comparatively higher region (3450 cm^{-1}) indicating a weaker or less extensive H-bonding network in the compound and is expectedly so, as the lattice water which is absent in it, plays very important role in the formation of H-bonding network in **1**.

Experimental

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer and the copper content in the complex was estimated spectrophotometrically⁴. IR spectra in KBr ($4500\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. The thermal analyses (TG-DTA) were carried out on a Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA 851 thermal analyzer in a dynamic atmosphere of nitrogen (flow rate : $30\text{ cm}^3\text{ min}^{-1}$). The sample was heated in an alumina crucible at a rate of 5° min^{-1} .

Preparation and crystallisation of the $[\text{Cu}(\text{L-glu})(\text{H}_2\text{O})].\text{H}_2\text{O}$: To a methanolic (25 ml) solution containing L-glutamic acid (0.736 g, 5 mmol) was added $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2.6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.85 g, 5 mmol) at 50° . The resulting solution was adjusted to $\text{pH} = 5$ by addition of methanolic solution (5 ml) of triethyl amine (1.4 cm^3 , 10 mmol). The desired blue crystalline compound was immediately precipitated. Single crystals, suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by slow evaporation of very diluted water solution of the complex **1**. Yield 0.88 g. (72%) (Found : C, 25.01; H, 4.63; N, 5.28; Cu, 25.13. Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{CuNO}_5.\text{H}_2\text{O}$: C, 24.52; H, 4.49; N, 5.72; Cu, 25.95%).

Crystallography : 4664 reflections were measured with $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation using the MARresearch Image Plate System of which 1472 were independent. The crystals were positioned at 70 mm from the Image Plate. 100 frames were measured at 2° intervals with a counting time of 2 mins. Data analysis was carried out with the XDS program⁵. The structure was solved using direct methods with the Shelx86 program⁶. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms bonded to carbon were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. The hydrogen atoms bonded to oxygen were located in a difference Fourier map and refined with distance constraints. An em-

pirical absorption correction was carried out using the DIF-ABS program⁷. The structure was refined on F^2 using Shelxl⁸ to $R/$ 0.0453, $wR2$ 0.1149; for 1409 reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$.

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